

1 **Differences in temperature response of phenological development among diverse Ethiopian**
2 **sorghum genotypes are linked to racial grouping and agro-ecological adaptation**

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19 **ABSTRACT**

20 Sorghum is an important dryland crop in the semi-arid tropics, and temperature and photoperiod are
21 main environmental factors affecting phenology and hence adaptation. The objectives of this study
22 were to quantify the response of development rate to temperature and photoperiod for 19 diverse
23 Ethiopian sorghum genotypes, and determine if differences in these responses could be linked to
24 racial grouping or agro-ecological adaptation. The genotypes, representing four major sorghum races
25 and adaptation to four agro-ecological zones, were sown on twelve dates at two locations in Ethiopia
26 with contrasting altitude. This created a range in photoperiod and temperatures relevant to Ethiopian
27 conditions. Days from emergence to flag leaf appearance, anthesis, and maturity were recorded. A
28 predictive phenology modeling framework was used to fit the effects of photoperiod and temperature
29 on the rate of development for both the pre- and post-anthesis periods. Results indicated that pre-
30 anthesis development rate was independent of photoperiod for the range tested. This result differed
31 from west-african germplasm, and likely reflects differences in agro-ecological adaptation and racial
32 background. Significant genotypic differences were observed for the base temperature (0 - 9.8°C) and
33 for the optimum rate of development (0.011 - 0.022 d⁻¹, with low value indicating late anthesis), with
34 differences related to agro-ecology and racial type. Post-anthesis differences in the temperature
35 response were minor. The observed differences in pre-anthesis base temperature can positively impact
36 sorghum breeding programs globally, especially in temperate regions where suitability for early
37 spring plantings is often restricted by low temperatures.

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39 Key-words: anthesis; base temperature; earliness; photoperiod response; sorghum race.

40 **INTRODUCTION**

41 Phenology is an important component of agro-ecological adaptation of cereals like sorghum
42 [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench]. Variation in developmental responses to environmental conditions

43 among genotypes planted at the same location and time will result in genotypes reaching critical
44 phenological stages at different times. They can thus experience different growth environments,
45 which can ultimately affect grain yield (Hammer et al., 1989). Climate change is likely to exacerbate
46 this issue, particularly if changes in environmental conditions will affect grain yield through effects
47 on crop duration or on the likelihood of heat stress occurring around anthesis (Lobell et al., 2015;
48 Singh et al., 2017). While crop adaptation analysis can be significantly enhanced via crop modelling
49 and simulation (Hammer et al., 2016), prediction of phenological development is critical for proper
50 simulation of the performance of a crop in a particular target environment (Birch et al., 1998; Ravi
51 Kumar et al., 2009). This requires accurate quantification of temperature and photoperiod responses
52 for phenological development under field conditions (Birch et al., 1998).

53 In the absence of drought stress, temperature and photoperiod are the two main environmental
54 factors affecting phenology in sorghum (Caddel and Weibel, 1971; Quinby et al., 1973; Gerik and
55 Miller, 1984; Hammer et al., 1989; Craufurd et al., 1999; Clerget et al., 2008; Ravi Kumar et al.,
56 2009). Sorghum is a short-day crop, such that its rate of development is hastened under short
57 photoperiods. Quantitative studies on a set of hybrid sorghums revealed that rate of development was
58 hastened at photoperiods less than 13-13.5 h. (Hammer et al., 1989; Ravi Kumar et al., 2009). Studies
59 conducted on landraces in West Africa showed a very strong response of timing of anthesis to
60 photoperiod within a narrow photoperiod range of 12-13.5 h. (Grenier et al., 2001; Clerget et al.,
61 2004, 2008). In general, sorghum germplasm originating from lower latitudes is more photoperiod
62 sensitive than germplasm from higher latitudes (Craufurd et al., 1999; Grenier et al., 2001) and many
63 improved hybrids adapted to temperate zones have limited photoperiod sensitivity (Klein et al., 2008).

64 Thermal time has been used effectively as a means to quantify development and capture
65 temperature responsiveness in a predictive framework. The response to temperature of the rate of
66 development prior to anthesis of sorghum is adequately described by a bilinear relationship, where
67 development ceases if temperature drops below a base temperature (T_{base}) or exceeds the maximum

68 temperature (T_{max}) and the rate of development is optimum (R_{opt}) at T_{opt} (Hammer et al., 1993).
69 Studies have determined cardinal temperatures for calculation of thermal time for development in
70 sorghum as 11°C, 30°C, and 42°C for T_{base} , T_{opt} , and T_{max} respectively (Alagarswamy et al., 1986;
71 Hammer et al., 1993; Ravi Kumar et al., 2009). Several studies have reported significant genotypic
72 differences for sorghum in the response of development rate to temperature, in particular for T_{base} and
73 T_{opt} (Hammer et al., 1989; Craufurd et al., 1998, 1999). However, particularly for T_{base} the observed
74 differences are generally small, despite inclusion of genotypes from contrasting agro-ecologies in
75 some of these studies (Craufurd et al., 1999). This led Craufurd et al. (1999) to the conclusion that
76 T_{base} of sorghum is very conservative, a view that was also put forward in more general terms by
77 Parent and Tardieu (2012). However, larger differences in T_{base} have been observed for crops like rice
78 (*Oryza sativa* L.) (Dingkuhn and Miezán, 1995) and soybean (*Glycine max*) (Roberts et al., 1996).
79 Moreover, post-anthesis cardinal temperatures for rate of development of sorghum differ substantially
80 from those before anthesis, and have been identified as 5.7°C and 23.5°C for T_{base} and T_{opt}
81 respectively (Hammer and Muchow, 1994). Hence, it is likely that a larger range in the response of
82 pre-anthesis development to temperature is present in sorghum germplasm.

83 Sorghum is believed to have originated in north eastern Africa, in an area currently occupied
84 by Ethiopia and Sudan (Damon, 1962; FAO, 1995). This is supported by the wide range of sorghum
85 races cultivated in the region and the diverse forms of wild and weedy sorghum species still prevalent
86 in this area (Damon, 1962; Grenier et al., 2004; Tesso et al., 2008). The racial distribution in this area
87 can be markedly different across regions as shown by Grenier et al. (2004) for Sudan. This is likely
88 associated with the wide range in growing conditions, as morphological variation of sorghum from
89 Ethiopia and Eritrea is linked to their adaptation zone, rather than their geographical region of origin
90 (Ayana and Bekele, 1999). In Ethiopia, the agro-ecological zones where sorghum is grown can vary
91 widely in altitude, rainfall, and growing duration (Ayana and Bekele, 2000). This combination of
92 wide agro-ecological and genetic diversity in Ethiopia provides an excellent opportunity to screen for

93 genotypic variability in sorghum for parameters that determine the response of development rate to
94 temperature, and to quantify genotypic differences in this response.

95 Quantitative knowledge of developmental responses is essential to predict timing of flowering
96 and hence biomass production and grain yield (Hammer et al., 2010), This is particularly important
97 in environments with variable timing and intensity of abiotic stress, where variation in phenology can
98 result in significant genotype \times environment interactions for grain yield (Hammer et al., 2014).
99 Therefore, the objectives of this study were to (1) quantify the response of development rate to
100 temperature and check for the presence of photoperiod sensitivity using an existing predictive
101 phenology modelling framework for diverse Ethiopian sorghum germplasm, and (2) link these
102 differences to racial background and agro-ecological adaptation zones for this germplasm.

103 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

104 A set of 19 local sorghum genotypes was grown in serial sowing experiments that were
105 conducted at two locations with contrasting altitude (temperature). Observations on phenological
106 stages were recorded, and analyses undertaken to quantify responses to temperature and photoperiod.
107 Although the natural range in photoperiod in Ethiopia is narrow (Fig. 1), photoperiod-sensitive
108 sorghum germplasm from sub-Saharan West Africa is highly response to photoperiod within this
109 same range (Chanterreau et al., 2001; Clerget et al., 2008).

110 **Genetic material and classification**

111 A set of 19 diverse Ethiopian genotypes, including landraces and improved varieties that are
112 adapted to the four major sorghum growing areas in Ethiopia, were used in the experiments (Table
113 1). The classification of these sorghum growing areas is based on differences in altitude (meters above
114 sea level, masl), rainfall (mm), and duration of the growing period (days), and comprises of the
115 highlands (>1900 masl, 800 mm, 170-200 days), intermediate zone (1600-1900 masl, >1000 mm,

116 150-180 days), wet lowlands (<1600 masl, > 1000 mm, 110-150 days) and the dry lowlands (<1600
117 masl, <600 mm, 90-130 days) (Ayana and Bekele, 2000).

118 To characterise the genotypes according to their racial alignment, their deoxyribose nucleic
119 acid (DNA) profiles were compared with that of a larger set of germplasm from Ethiopia. Total
120 genomic DNA was extracted from bulked young leaves of five plants of 553 genotypes from the
121 Ethiopian sorghum breeding program, including 18 of the 19 genotypes included in this study,
122 following the procedure described by DArT (Diversity Arrays Technology) P/L (DArT,
123 www.diversityarrays.com). The samples were genotyped following an integrated DArT and
124 genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) methodology, involving complexity reduction of the genomic
125 DNA to remove repetitive sequences using methylation sensitive restriction enzymes prior to
126 sequencing on Next Generation sequencing platforms (DArT, www.diversityarrays.com). The
127 sequence data generated were then aligned to the most recent version (v3.1.1) of the sorghum
128 reference genome sequence (Paterson et al., 2009) to identify SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism)
129 markers. The genetic linkage location was predicted based on the sorghum genetic linkage consensus
130 map (Mace et al., 2008). In total, 35,383 genome wide SNPs were reported.

131 Population genetic structure of the sorghum lines was analysed using a structure-like
132 population genetic analyses in the R package LEA (Francois, 2016). The number of clusters was
133 determined using a cross-entropy criterion (K). The cross-entropy criterion is based on the prediction
134 of a fraction of masked genotypes (matrix completion) and on the cross validation approach (Francois,
135 2016), with smaller values of the cross-entropy criterion indicating a better fit of the number of
136 clusters to the underlying data. We performed runs for 9 values of K (K=2:10), and selected the value
137 of K for which the cross-entropy curve exhibited a plateau.

138 Results of the structure analysis were used to identify genotypes representing the different
139 sorghum races including *durra*, *caudatum*, *kafir*, and *guinea*. The Sokal and Michener dissimilarity
140 index was used to generate dissimilarity matrices (Sokal and Michener, 1958) based on SNP markers.

141 Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) was used to investigate the overall variation and patterns within
142 and between the races using DARwin 6.0 statistical software (Perrier and Jacquemoud-Collet, 2006).

143 **Experiment details**

144 The 19 genotypes were sown on six dates at two locations in each of two years to create a
145 range in photoperiod (PP) and temperature relevant to Ethiopian conditions. The two locations,
146 Melkassa (1046 m, 8°25'N, 39°19'E) and Kulumsa (2259 m, 8°01'N, 39°09'E), represent lowland
147 and highland altitudes respectively. They differed little in PP at any time as they had comparable
148 latitude, but due to the difference in altitude, temperatures at Kulumsa (5-29°C) were consistently
149 lower than at Melkassa (16-35°C) (Fig.1). Sowing dates ranged from March to July in 2013 and April
150 to July in 2014, with three weeks between successive sowing dates. The use of similar sowing dates
151 across the two locations yielded temperature differences that were independent of PP, whereas the
152 range in sowing date × location combinations gave a wide range in temperature conditions. The PP
153 around emergence ranged from 12.9 h (including twilight) for the experiment sown late in March
154 2013, to 13.4 h for June sowings (Fig. 1). Because West-African sorghum landraces can exhibit a
155 significant PP response even within a narrow PP range (Miller et al., 1968; Clerget et al., 2008), the
156 current experiments enabled determination of the presence or absence of similar PP sensitivity in
157 Ethiopian germplasm within a PP range relevant to Ethiopian growing conditions.

158 The genotypes were sown in a randomised complete block design with two replications. Each
159 genotype was sown in a single row plot of 5 m length, with a 0.75 m distance between plots (rows)
160 and 1.5m distance between blocks. Each sowing date and location had its own randomisation. During
161 sowing, the seeds were manually drilled into the rows and at *ca.* 20 days after emergence, excess
162 seedlings were thinned to 0.15 m distance between plants. The recommended rate of phosphorus
163 fertilizer (46 kg ha⁻¹ P₂O₅) in the form of di-ammonium phosphate and nitrogen fertilizer (23 kg ha⁻¹
164 nitrogen as urea) were applied at sowing and at 35 days after sowing, respectively. The experiments
165 were well watered and no symptoms of drought stress were evident in any of the experiments.

166

Observations

167 The dates of emergence, full flag leaf expansion, anthesis, and physiological maturity were
 168 recorded in all treatments and data have been supplied in the supplementary material. Emergence date
 169 was recorded when 50% of the seedlings in a plot had emerged. Around two weeks after emergence,
 170 when *ca.* five leaves had fully expanded, three representative plants in each plot were tagged to record
 171 the timing of development stages. The date of full flag leaf expansion of each plant was estimated as
 172 the date that the ligule of the flag leaf became visible above the ligule of the previous leaf. Anthesis
 173 was recorded when 50% of the anthers of a main shoot were visible, and physiological maturity was
 174 recorded when seeds at the base of the main shoot panicle showed a black layer (Hammer and
 175 Muchow, 1994). No data on phenological stages were recorded for the 6th sowing at Melkassa in
 176 2013, leaving a total of 23 experiments (location × year × sowing date combinations) for analyses.
 177 Daily minimum and maximum air temperatures were recorded from nearby weather stations at both
 178 locations.

179

Fitting models for rate of development

180 For each genotype, the effect of temperature and photoperiod on the daily rate of development (R)
 181 from emergence to anthesis and from anthesis to maturity was analysed using the optimisation
 182 program DEVEL2 (Holzworth and Hammer, 1996; Ravi Kumar et al., 2009). Data were combined
 183 across locations, years, and sowing dates, to fit the equation

184

$$185 \text{ Rate (day}^{-1}\text{)} = R_{\text{opt}} \times f(\text{T}) \times f(\text{PP}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

186

187 where R_{opt} is the daily rate of development under optimal temperature and photoperiod, and
 188 $f(\text{T})$ and $f(\text{PP})$ are functions of daily temperature and photoperiod, respectively, and take values
 189 between 0 and 1. The inverse of R_{opt} represents the minimum number of days required from

190 emergence to reach anthesis, which occurs when both T and PP are at optimum values, so that $f(T)$
191 and $f(PP)$ each have a value of 1. For $f(T)$, a broken-linear response function was used to define the
192 response to temperature in terms of T_{base} , T_{opt} , and T_{max} (Hammer et al., 1993). The function takes
193 values of 0 for $T < T_{base}$ and $T > T_{max}$ and has a value of 1 at $T = T_{opt}$. For $f(PP)$, a triple broken linear
194 function was used to define the response to photoperiod in terms of a lower critical PP (PPc_l), upper
195 critical PP (PPc_u), and the slope of the responsiveness to PP between these two levels (PPr) (Major,
196 1980). Because sorghum is a short-day plant, $f(PP)$ takes a value of 1 when $PP < PPc_l$, indicating a
197 faster rate of development under short day length. As in Ravi Kumar et al. (2009), to allow for
198 situations when the temperature moves across cardinal values of $f(T)$ during the day, 3-h temperature,
199 rather than daily mean temperature, was used in calculating the value of $f(T)$ for each day. Calculation
200 of 3-h temperature was based on the method reported by Jones and Kiniry (1986) using cubic
201 interpolation from minimum and maximum daily temperatures.

202 In order to develop a model for the daily rate of development of Ethiopian germplasm between
203 emergence and anthesis, previously determined coefficients for T_{base} , T_{opt} , and T_{max} of 11°C, 30°C,
204 and 42°C respectively (Hammer et al., 1993) were used as a starting point for $f(T)$, whereas R_{opt} and
205 parameters for $f(PP)$ were optimised for each genotype. Optimisations were done across all 19
206 genotypes and the total sum of squares of residuals (ΣSSR) calculated and divided by the appropriate
207 degrees of freedom (df) to obtain a mean squared residual (MSR). Next, optimisations of parameters
208 for $f(T)$ were included for individual genotypes by optimising T_{base} , T_{opt} , and R_{opt} . T_{max} was fixed at
209 42°C (Hammer et al., 1993), as a lack of data at high temperatures (Fig. 1) did not allow optimisation
210 for this parameter, whereas parameterisation for $f(PP)$ was based on results for the initial runs. The
211 MSR with this parameterisation for individual genotypes was calculated and an analysis of covariance
212 was conducted to determine if a significant improvement in goodness of fit resulted from inclusion
213 of genotype-specific parameters for T_{base} , T_{opt} . This was done with an F-test that checked if the MSR
214 of the combined model was significantly greater than the MSR using the model with genotype specific

215 parameter estimates, where MSR was calculated as the ratio between Σ SSR and total degrees of
216 freedom across all genotypes. Subsequent optimisations were undertaken to similarly determine if
217 the effects of having a common T_{base} or T_{opt} across all genotypes affected the goodness of fit. This
218 was done by identifying the common T_{base} or T_{opt} with the lowest Σ SSR across all genotypes, followed
219 by an F-test that compared the MSR of the combined model with the MSR using the model with
220 genotype specific parameter estimates.

221 A similar approach was used to determine cardinal temperatures for the development rate
222 during the period from anthesis to physiological maturity, employing a previously defined thermal
223 time model that used default coefficients of 5.7°C and 23.5°C for T_{base} and T_{opt} respectively, as
224 starting values (Hammer and Muchow, 1994). In this case, the model had no T_{max} . Because not all
225 plants reached physiological maturity under the cool conditions at Kulumsa, only 16 genotypes were
226 used in this analysis. In addition, the accumulated thermal time (TT, °Cd) from full flag leaf expansion
227 to anthesis was calculated based on the optimised cardinal temperature values found for emergence
228 to anthesis for each genotype.

229 For parameters for which genotype specific values were used, genotypes were classified into
230 five groups based on their racial group and agro-ecological adaptation (Table 1), and average values
231 across the genotypes within each group were calculated. The significance of differences in average
232 parameter values between two groups was based on a t-test using pooled method for equal variances,
233 using SAS Enterprise Guide 9.4 (SAS, 2013).

234

235 **RESULTS**

236 **Sorghum racial grouping**

237 The genetic structure analysis across 553 Ethiopian germplasm lines resulted in an optimum
238 K value of 6, based on the cross entropy criterion (Fig. 2). These six groups corresponded to the

239 previously known races of *caudatum*, *kafir*, *guinea*, East African *durra*, and Asian *durra*, plus an
240 additional grouping of *durra* races for genotypes primarily from the highland parts of Ethiopia (Fig.
241 2). The Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) reflected the racial group classifications identified
242 through the structure analysis, with racial group membership defined as $\geq 80\%$ of the genome
243 classified as a single racial type. The separate clustering of Ethiopian *durras* in Fig. 2 was in
244 agreement with previous studies by Brown et al. (2011) and Mace et al. (2008) who both identified
245 multiple groups within the *durra* types, indicating that *durras* from Ethiopia form a separate grouping
246 from other *durras* such as those from India.

247 Of the 18 genotypes included in this study that were racially classified, 16 were classified as
248 either *caudatum*, *kafir*, or Ethiopian highland *durra* (Table 1). For 12 of these 16 genotypes, at least
249 99% of their genome belonged to a single racial group, whereas for Macia (96.9% *caudatum*),
250 Birmash (94.1% *kafir*), and Jamiyu (91.2% Ethiopian highland *durra*) this was at least 90%.
251 Geremew (80.7% *kafir*) also contained 11.0% Ethiopian highland *durra* and 7.1% *caudatum*. The
252 two mixed race genotypes contained mainly *caudatum* and *guinea*, with Adukura having 50%
253 *caudatum* and 22% *guinea*, and Bobe Red 63% *caudatum* and 22% *guinea*. These were also the only
254 two genotypes that contained at least 5% of *guinea* and east African *durra* in their genome (Table 1).
255 None of the genotypes contained more than 5% Asian *durra*, although Adukara had 4.7%.

256 The identified racial groups for the genotypes were closely associated with the four major
257 agro-ecological adaptation zones for sorghum in Ethiopia and with the germplasm type (Table 1).
258 Among the released varieties, those with adaptation to dry lowlands were all *caudatum*, whereas those
259 with adaptation to intermediate altitude were all *kafir* (Table 1, Fig. 2). Among the landraces, the two
260 that were adapted to wet lowlands were both mixed race, whereas landraces adapted to dry lowlands
261 and improved landraces adapted to highlands were all *durra* (Table 1, Fig. 2). Hence, for the
262 germplasm adapted to dry lowlands, the released varieties (*caudatum*) belonged to a different racial
263 group than the landraces (*durra*). Conversely, the *durra* race was the only one that contained

264 germplasm with different agro-ecological adaptation. The first two components of the principal
265 coordinate analysis (PCoA) explained 20.0% of the total variation, with 14.9% associated with the
266 first component and 5.1% with the 2nd component, respectively (Fig. 2).

267 **Genotypes showed no response to photoperiod between emergence and anthesis**

268 There was no obvious effect of photoperiod on the daily rate of development from emergence
269 to anthesis over the PP range included. Fig. 3 presents averaged data for this period for Meko and
270 Jigurti, but similar results were obtained for the other genotypes. In general, the rate of development
271 was greater at Melkassa than Kulumsa, but within location, there was no association with
272 photoperiod. The slightly greater rate of development at Kulumsa under short PP compared to long
273 PP was associated with slightly higher temperatures experienced by experiments sown at shorter PP
274 compared with those sown under longer PP (Fig. 3). This was confirmed by the fitting procedure for
275 the daily rate of development (Eq. 1), which showed that inclusion of a photoperiod response did not
276 yield any significant improvement in fit in any of the genotypes. Hence, no photoperiod response was
277 included in any of the subsequent analyses.

278 **Genotypes differed in their response to temperature between emergence and anthesis**

279 In contrast, temperature strongly affected the daily development rate of Ethiopian germplasm,
280 as the slower rate at Kulumsa compared to Melkassa was associated with lower average temperatures
281 at Kulumsa. This is illustrated in Fig. 3 for Meko and Jigurti. Within locations, the average rate of
282 development for the whole period from emergence to anthesis increased with average daily
283 temperature over this period at Kulumsa, but not at Melkassa. This was because Fig. 3 uses the
284 average temperature for the entire pre-flowering period, rather than daily temperature data that were
285 used in fitting cardinal temperatures for the daily rate of development function (Eq. 1). Hence, the
286 weak association at Melkassa was a consequence of the observation that daily maximum temperature
287 at that location (Fig. 1) often exceeded T_{opt} for the rate of development (section 2.4), such that higher

288 maximum temperatures delayed the rate of development. Across the range of environments studied,
 289 fitting previously determined coefficients for T_{base} (11°C) and T_{opt} (30°C) to the model, while
 290 optimising R_{opt} for each genotype, yielded ΣSSR of 14.11 and MSR of 0.03485 (df=405). However,
 291 optimising both T_{base} and T_{opt} independently for each genotype, in addition to R_{opt} , reduced both the
 292 ΣSSR (1.85) and MSR (0.00505, df=367) and the difference was highly significant ($F=6.90$, $P<0.01$).
 293 There was a considerable genotypic range observed in R_{opt} and T_{base} , but less for T_{opt} (data not shown).
 294 In order to determine if a common T_{opt} could be used across genotypes, optimisations were repeated
 295 with a common T_{opt} ranging from 23°C to 31°C while optimising individual values of R_{opt} and T_{base}
 296 for each genotype. Results indicated that a common T_{opt} of 27°C gave the best fit (Fig. 4) with only
 297 a minor increase in ΣSSR (1.86) compared to the model where T_{opt} was optimised for each genotype
 298 independently, but a reduction in MSR (0.00482) because of greater df (386). Hence, a common T_{opt}
 299 of 27°C was adopted for the subsequent test of whether a common T_{base} value could also be adopted.
 300 Optimisations were conducted by fixing T_{base} to a value ranging from 0°C to 9°C, while optimising
 301 R_{opt} for each genotype. The results indicated that a common T_{base} of 6°C gave the best fit if a common
 302 T_{opt} of 27°C was used. However, the MSR increased to 0.00658, which was a significant increase
 303 over the fit with independent T_{base} values for each genotype (0.00482) ($F=1.36$, $P<0.05$). Hence, T_{base}
 304 and R_{opt} were optimised for each genotype using common values across genotypes for T_{opt} (27°C)
 305 and T_{max} (42°C).

306 Optimising T_{base} and R_{opt} for individual genotypes generally yielded good fits for the model.
 307 The R^2 ranged from 0.79 (Chiro) to 0.93 (Geremew and IS9302) and 15 out of 19 genotypes had
 308 values of $R^2 > 0.85$ (Table 2). Importantly, across all individual genotype \times location \times year \times sowing
 309 date combinations, the model predicted the observed time to anthesis well, with an R^2 of 0.94 and
 310 RMSE of 7.2 days (Fig. 5). There was a minor bias, as the slope of the regression was slightly below
 311 unity (0.94 ± 0.022 , 5% confidence interval), which was offset by a significantly positive intercept

312 (7.43±2.43). If the regression was forced through the origin, the slope was 1.00±0.006, with minimal
 313 changes in the RMSE (7.5 days).

314 Among genotypes, values for T_{base} ranged from 0-0.1°C for Melkam, Chelenko, and ETS2752,
 315 to 9.8°C for Birmash, with an average of 4.6°C (Table 2). The R_{opt} ranged from 0.011 d⁻¹ (late
 316 anthesis) for Adukara and Chelenko to 0.022 d⁻¹ (early anthesis) for Meko (Table 2). This indicated
 317 that late genotypes took about twice as many days to reach anthesis as the early genotypes.
 318 Importantly, the genotypic differences in both T_{base} and R_{opt} were significantly related to the racial
 319 type and agro-ecology of their adaptation. On average, the *caudatum* and *kafir* genotypes had
 320 significantly greater R_{opt} (earlier anthesis) than the highland *durra* and mixed race genotypes, whereas
 321 *caudatum* and highland *durra* genotypes had significantly lower T_{base} than *kafir* and mixed race
 322 genotypes (Table 2). The dry lowland *durra* genotypes on average had a high R_{opt} (early anthesis)
 323 that did not differ significantly from that of the *caudatum* and *kafir* groups, but an intermediate T_{base}
 324 (Table 2). In terms of agro-ecological adaptation, the dry lowland *caudatum* (released varieties) and
 325 *durra* (landraces) groups both had high R_{opt} , whereas the landraces adapted to the wetter areas, like
 326 the highlands (*durra*) and wet lowlands (*caudatum/guinea* mixed race) generally had low R_{opt} .

327 **Thermal time from full flag leaf expansion to anthesis and anthesis to maturity**

328 For the period between full flag leaf expansion and anthesis, the average accumulated thermal
 329 time ranged from 151°Cd to 322°Cd across all genotypes (Table 2). This range reflected genotypic
 330 differences in T_{base} , as the greatest values were recorded for genotypes with the lowest T_{base} (Fig. 6).
 331 Hence, genotypic differences in the duration of this period were small if expressed in number of days.
 332 From the regression in Fig. 6, it can be derived that for genotypes with a T_{base} in the range of 0-10°C,
 333 the difference in number of days for the duration of this period was < 2 days if the average daily
 334 temperature was in the range of 17-21°C.

335 For the period from anthesis to physiological maturity, optimisation of T_{base} and T_{opt} resulted
336 in parameter values ranging from 0°C to 8°C for T_{base} and from 19°C to 30°C for T_{opt} across the 16
337 genotypes for which data were available. However, use of specific values for individual genotypes
338 did not significantly improve the fitted model (data not shown) when compared to the fit with the
339 previously determined coefficients of 5.7°C and 23.5°C for T_{base} and T_{opt} respectively (Hammer and
340 Muchow, 1994). Hence, the common values were used and R_{opt} optimised for each genotype.
341 Genotypic differences in R_{opt} were generally small (Table 3), particularly in comparison to differences
342 in R_{opt} prior to anthesis. A common model across all genotypes yielded R_{opt} of 0.023 ($R^2=0.44$,
343 $P<0.0001$).

344 DISCUSSION

345 Photoperiod response was not evident for range tested

346 The rate of phenological development of the Ethiopian germplasm used in this study was not
347 significantly affected by photoperiod (including twilight) of up to 13.4 h (Figs. 1 and 3). This result
348 contrasts starkly with West African sorghum genotypes, which are grown at latitudes similar to
349 Ethiopia, yet show a very strong response to photoperiod, even within a narrow range of photoperiods
350 similar to the one in this study (Miller et al., 1968; Chantereau et al., 2001; Clerget et al., 2008). This
351 difference in photoperiod response could well be a consequence of differing environmental drivers
352 for adaptation. In the sorghum belt of West Africa, the rainy season generally has a variable onset,
353 but a much more distinct end and the duration can range from *ca.* 40 days to well over 100 days
354 (Kouressy et al., 2008; Frappart et al., 2009). In order to minimise the effects of pests and diseases
355 on maturing grains, it is important for crops to reach anthesis towards the end of the rainy season,
356 irrespective of sowing date (Clerget et al., 2008). To achieve that at latitudes where the range in
357 daylength is small (Fig. 1) and where the sowing date can be highly variable, adapted germplasm
358 generally is very photoperiod sensitive above a threshold photoperiod (Chantereau et al., 2001;

359 Dingkuhn et al., 2008; Kouressy et al., 2008) to ensure homeostasis of anthesis around the end of the
360 rainy season (Kassam and Andrews, 1975; Dingkuhn et al., 2008). This photoperiod sensitivity is
361 closely adapted to latitude, with high photoperiod sensitivity generally more prevalent for germplasm
362 from lower latitudes (Craufurd et al., 1999; Grenier et al., 2001) to account for the smaller range in
363 photoperiod.

364 The observation that this previously reported relationship between latitude and photoperiod
365 sensitivity does not hold for the comparison between West African and Ethiopian germplasm may
366 also be associated with a difference in racial background in addition to the eco-geographical
367 conditions. The photoperiod sensitive germplasm used in West Africa is predominantly *guinea* type
368 (Rattunde et al., 2013), whereas in the current study, most genotypes were *caudatum*, *durra*, or *kafir*
369 types, with only the two mixed race genotypes (Adukara and Bobe Red) containing some *guinea*
370 germplasm. A stratification of the sorghum core-collection based on eco-geographical data (Grenier
371 et al., 2001) showed that within races, the association between latitude and photoperiod sensitivity
372 was maintained. However, for latitudes up to 20°N, which includes all of Ethiopia, the *guinea* race
373 had a greater proportion of germplasm with medium to high photoperiod sensitivity than the
374 *caudatum*, *durra*, and particularly *kafir* races (Grenier et al., 2001). Consistent with this, Craufurd et
375 al. (1999) observed that for West African sorghum there is a relationship between minimum time to
376 anthesis and latitude, whereas for East African sorghum there is not. This lack of photoperiod
377 sensitivity in Ethiopian germplasm implies that this trait is not as critical for adaptation in Ethiopia
378 as in West Africa. As photoperiod regulation confers little advantage for sorghum adaptation in
379 Ethiopian germplasm, current results show that photoperiod response is associated with agro-
380 ecological adaptation and not solely with latitude.

381 **Genotypic differences in temperature response prior to anthesis were related to race and**
 382 **agro-ecological adaptation**

383 Significant genotypic variation in the response of development to temperature for the phase
 384 from emergence to anthesis was observed, with variation in both R_{opt} (minimum days to anthesis) and
 385 T_{base} (Table 2). The range in R_{opt} across the 19 genotypes was two-fold, indicating that the earliest
 386 genotypes reached anthesis in *ca.* half the number of days required for the latest genotypes. T_{base}
 387 ranged from 0 to 9.8°C. Whereas genotypic differences in R_{opt} (earliness) are routinely reported
 388 (Craufurd et al., 1998, 1999; Ravi Kumar et al., 2009), reports of differences in T_{base} are scant. Wade
 389 et al. (1993) observed significant genotypic variation in T_{base} (5.9°C to 9.8°C) and in temperature
 390 responsiveness among diverse sorghum hybrids, but that was for germination rate. Other studies have
 391 also revealed some genotypic variation in T_{base} (Hammer et al., 1989; Craufurd et al., 1999) for other
 392 developmental stages, but to a lesser extent than found here. Although estimates for T_{base} in this study
 393 were based on extrapolations from the observed range in temperatures (Fig. 1), covariate analysis
 394 indicated that genotypic differences in T_{base} were significant. Moreover, the estimated T_{base} was
 395 consistently below 10°C (Table 2), and these values gave a significantly ($P < 0.01$) better fit than the
 396 11°C observed for Indian and Australian germplasm (Hammer et al., 1989; Ravi Kumar et al., 2009).
 397 In contrast, the common value for T_{opt} of 27°C was consistent with the value reported by Craufurd et
 398 al. (1998). Parent and Tardieu (2012) have suggested that the response of development rates to
 399 temperature is conservative across and within species. While our analysis suggests this may not be
 400 the case for this set of Ethiopian germplasm, controlled experimentation across a wider range of
 401 temperatures is required to confirm this finding.

402 The veracity of the genotypic differences in T_{base} and R_{opt} was supported by their association
 403 with the racial background and the agroecology of their origin. The *caudatum* and *kafir* groups both
 404 had high R_{opt} , but *kafir* had significantly higher T_{base} than *caudatum* (Table 2). Highland *durras* and
 405 mixed races from the wet lowlands had low R_{opt} , but highland *durras* had significantly lower T_{base}

406 (Table 2). In general, landraces from the highlands and wet lowlands tended to have low R_{opt} ,
 407 indicating late anthesis. Both these landrace groups are adapted to regions with high rainfall, where
 408 drought is unlikely to occur (Nida et al., 2014), such that biomass accumulation is radiation limited
 409 (Hammer et al., 2010). Under such agro-ecologies, late anthesis will increase the total amount of
 410 intercepted radiation and hence biomass production and grain yield. In addition, the low T_{base} of the
 411 highland *durra* racial group allows development to proceed at higher rates under low temperatures
 412 compared to germplasm with higher T_{base} . Because temperatures are generally lower at higher
 413 altitudes, as illustrated by the differences between Melkassa and Kulumsa (Fig. 1), the low T_{base} of
 414 the highland *durra* landraces thus provides specific adaptation to the agro-ecological conditions of
 415 the region where they are grown. One of the genotypes in this group, Alemaya 70, was reported to
 416 have high levels of cold tolerance in terms of early establishment and germination (Singh, 1985).
 417 Similarly, the intermediate T_{base} for the dry lowland released varieties, which are also of the Ethiopian
 418 highland *durra* race (Table 2), could accelerate the rate of development towards anthesis and thus
 419 allow potential escape of end-of-season drought stress under dryland conditions. Importantly, it
 420 would also permit earlier sowing in spring, which could similarly allow escape of drought stress in
 421 environments with dry summers. In contrast, the high T_{base} of the landraces from the wet lowlands
 422 (*caudatum/guinea* mixed race types) may reflect the agroecology of an environment where in the
 423 absence of drought, biomass production and hence yield is limited by radiation. A higher T_{base} is
 424 likely to reduce the rate of development towards anthesis and could thus be a mechanism to slightly
 425 delay anthesis. The observed differences in R_{opt} and T_{base} for the germplasm included in this study
 426 were closely associated with racial types (Table 2) and could have important implications for sorghum
 427 breeding globally.

428 For the period from full flag leaf expansion to anthesis, the observed genotypic variation in
 429 thermal time requirement was predominantly a consequence of differences in T_{base} , implying
 430 differences in duration amongst genotypes are small if duration is expressed in number of days. Based

431 on the regression in Fig. 6, it can be derived that if average daily temperatures are 20-22°C, the
 432 duration would be about 11.5-15.5 days if T_{base} ranges from 0-10°C. This is similar to values reported
 433 by van Oosterom et al. (2010) for Australian germplasm. However, Muchow and Carberry (1990)
 434 reported a thermal time target of 131°Cd using a T_{base} of 7°C, which is lower than the value of 192°Cd
 435 that can be derived from Fig. 6 using a similar T_{base} . In contrast, the target of 166°Cd reported by
 436 Ravi Kumar et al. (2009) using a T_{base} of 11°C is above the value of 125°Cd estimated from Fig. 6
 437 using the same T_{base} . Despite these differences in thermal targets across experiments, genotypic
 438 differences within experiments are generally small, particularly if duration is expressed in terms of
 439 days (Fig. 6; Muchow and Carberry, 1990; Ravi Kumar et al., 2009).

440 **Genotypic differences in the temperature response after anthesis were minor**

441 In contrast to the period prior to anthesis, the temperature response for the period from
 442 anthesis to maturity was similar to the response observed previously across a range of sorghum
 443 germplasm (Hammer and Muchow, 1994) as cardinal temperatures of 5.7°C (T_{base}) and 23.5°C (T_{opt})
 444 did not significantly reduce the goodness of fit compared to optimised data. Moreover, the duration
 445 of this period as observed by Ravi Kumar et al. (2009) of 723-839°Cd translates to an R_{opt} of 0.021-
 446 0.025 d⁻¹ (mean of 0.023 d⁻¹ or 43-44 days), which is similar to the results of Table 3. Although
 447 Hammer and Muchow (1994) reported a greater R_{opt} of 0.031 d⁻¹ (32 days) for a range of sorghum
 448 cultivars grown across three continents, their data also did not show any consistent genotypic
 449 differences for this trait. Significant differences in the duration of grain filling have been reported for
 450 sorghum by Yang et al. (2010), and these were associated with differences in individual grain size
 451 and mass. However, in that study, even a 230% increase in individual grain mass was associated with
 452 only a 25% increase in grain filling duration, indicating that grain filling rate accounted for most of
 453 the observed differences in grain mass. Hence, despite the large pre-anthesis genotypic differences in
 454 both cardinal temperatures and R_{opt} , there is only limited evidence of significant post-anthesis

455 genotypic differences for these parameters. This would indicate that temperature responses of these
456 two phenological phases are under different genetic control.

457 **CONCLUDING REMARKS**

458 This study has identified significant genotypic differences in the response of pre-anthesis
459 development to temperature, in particular with respect to T_{base} . Although the germplasm used was
460 specific to Ethiopia, the close association of the observed genotypic differences to racial grouping
461 and agro-ecological adaptation has global significance for sorghum cultivation. Ethiopian highland
462 *durra* types and *caudatum* types from the dry lowlands were identified as potential sources of low
463 T_{base} , which would indicate an ability to continue development at low temperatures. Such variation
464 could be explored through breeding, especially in temperate areas where suitability for early spring
465 planting is often restricted by low temperatures. The minor genotypic differences in the response of
466 post-anthesis phenological development to temperature indicates that selection for T_{base} during the
467 pre-anthesis period is unlikely to have any direct effects on grain filling duration. Implications on
468 grain yield of selecting for lower T_{base} are best explored through appropriate crop growth simulation
469 models that have the functionality to capture the genotype \times environment \times management interaction
470 effects on grain yield as an emergent consequence of crop growth and development dynamics. The
471 results of this study provide a basis for prediction of phenological development of Ethiopian
472 germplasm.

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REFERENCES

- 479
- 480 Alagarswamy, G., J.T. Ritchie, and B. Flint. 1986. Effect of high temperature on leaf appearance rates
481 in maize, rice, sorghum, and pearl millet. Agron. Abstr. American Society of Agronomy,
482 Madison, WI, p. 10.
- 483 Ayana, A., and E. Bekele. 1999. Multivariate analysis of morphological variation in sorghum
484 (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) germplasm from Ethiopia and Eritrea. Genetic Resources and
485 Crop Evolution 46:273-284.
- 486 Ayana, A., and E. Bekele. 2000. Geographical patterns of morphological variation in sorghum
487 (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) germplasm from Ethiopia and Eritrea: Quantitative
488 characters. Euphytica 115:91-104.
- 489 Birch, C.J., G.L. Hammer, and K.G. Rickert. 1998. Temperature and photoperiod sensitivity of
490 development in five cultivars of maize (*Zea mays* L.) from emergence to tassel initiation. Field
491 Crops Res. 55:93-107.
- 492 Brown, P.J., S. Myles, and S. Kresovich. 2011. Genetic support for phenotype-based racial
493 classification in sorghum. Crop Sci. 51:224-230. doi:10.2135/cropsci2010.03.0179
- 494 Caddel, J. L., and D.E. Weibel. 1971. Effect of photoperiod and temperature on the development of
495 sorghum. Agron. J. 63:799-803.
- 496 Chantereau, J., G. Trouche, J.F. Rami, M. Deu, C. Barro, and L. Grivet. 2001. RFLP mapping of
497 QTLs for photoperiod response in tropical sorghum. Euphytica 120:183-194.
- 498 Clerget, B., M. Dingkuhn, J. Chantereau, J. Hemberger, G. Louarn, and M. Vaksman. 2004. Does
499 panicle initiation in tropical sorghum depend on day-to-day change in photoperiod? Field
500 Crops Res. 88:11-27.

- 501 Clerget, B., M. Dingkuhn, E. Goze, H.F.W. Rattunde, and B. Ney. 2008. Variability of phyllochron,
502 plastochron and rate of increase in height in photoperiod-sensitive sorghum varieties. *Ann.*
503 *Bot.* 101:579-594.
- 504 Craufurd, P.Q., V. Mahalakshmi, F.R. Bidinger, S.Z. Mukuru, J. Chantereau, P.A. Omanga, A. Qi,
505 E.H. Roberts, R.H. Ellis, R.J. Summerfield, and G.L. Hammer. 1999. Adaptation of sorghum:
506 characterisation of genotypic flowering responses to temperature and photoperiod. *Theor.*
507 *Appl. Genet.* 99:900-911.
- 508 Craufurd, P.Q., A. Qi, R.H. Ellis, R.J. Summerfield, E.H. Roberts, and V. Mahalakshmi. 1998. Effect
509 of temperature on time to panicle initiation and leaf appearance in sorghum. *Crop Sci.* 38:942-
510 947.
- 511 Damon, E.G. 1962. The cultivated sorghums of Ethiopia: experiment station bulletin, 6, Imperial
512 Ethiopian College of agriculture and mechanical arts, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- 513 Dingkuhn, M., M. Kouressy, M. Vaksman, B. Clerget, and J. Chantereau. 2008. A model of sorghum
514 photoperiodism using the concept of threshold-lowering during prolonged appetence. *Eur. J.*
515 *Agron.* 28:74–89.
- 516 Dingkuhn, M., and K.M. Miezán. 1995. Climatic determinants of irrigated rice performance in the
517 Sahel — II. Validation of photothermal constants and characterization of genotypes. *Agric.*
518 *Syst.* 48:411-433.
- 519 Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). 1995. Sorghum and millets in human nutrition. Available
520 at: <http://www.fao.org/docrep/T0818e/T0818E00.htm> (Accessed 11 February 2020).
- 521 Francois, O. 2016. Running structure-like population genetic analyses with R. R tutorials in
522 population genetics, U. Grenoble-Alpes, 1-9.

- 523 Frappart, F., P. Hiernaux, F. Guichard, E. Mougin, L. Kergoat, M. Arjounin, F. Lavenue, M. Koité, J.-
524 E. Paturel, and T. Lebel. 2009. Rainfall regime across the Sahel band in the Gourma region,
525 Mali. *J. Hydrol.* 375:128-142.
- 526 Gerik, T.J., and F.R. Miller. 1984. Photoperiod and temperature effects on tropically and temperately-
527 adapted sorghum. *Field Crops Res.* 9:29-40.
- 528 Grenier, C., P.J. Bramel, J.A. Dahlberg, A. El-Ahmadi, M. Mahmoud, G.C. Peterson, D.T. Rosenow,
529 and G. Ejeta. 2004. Sorghums of the Sudan: analysis of regional diversity and distribution.
530 *Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution* 51:489–500.
- 531 Grenier, C., P.J. Bramel-Cox, and P. Hamon. 2001. Core collection of sorghum: I. Stratification based
532 on eco-geographical data. *Crop Sci.* 41:234-240.
- 533 Hammer, G.L., and R.C. Muchow. 1994. Assessing climatic risk to sorghum production in water-
534 limited subtropical environments. I. Development and testing of a simulation model. *Field*
535 *Crops Res.* 36:221-234.
- 536 Hammer, G.L., P.S. Carberry, and R.C. Muchow. 1993. Modelling genotypic and environmental
537 control of leaf area dynamics in grain sorghum. I. Whole plant level. *Field Crops Res.* 33:293-
538 310.
- 539 Hammer, G.L., G. McLean, S. Chapman, B. Zheng, A. Doherty, M.T. Harrison, E. van Oosterom,
540 and D. Jordan. 2014. Crop design for specific adaptation in variable dryland production
541 environments. *Crop and Pasture Sci.* 65:614-626.
- 542 Hammer, G.L., E.J. van Oosterom, G. McLean, S.C. Chapman, I. Broad, P. Harland, and R.C.
543 Muchow. 2010. Adapting APSIM to model the physiology and genetics of complex adaptive
544 traits in field crops. *J. Exp. Bot.* 61:2185-2202.

- 545 Hammer, G.L., G. McLean, A. Doherty, E.J. van Oosterom, and S. Chapman. 2016. Sorghum crop
546 modelling and its utility in agronomy and breeding. In: Ciampitti, I. and Prasad, V. (eds.).
547 Sorghum: state of the art and future perspectives. American Society of Agronomy and Crop
548 Science Society of America, Madison, WI United States, 1-25.
- 549 Hammer, G.L., R.L. Vanderlip, G. Gibson, L.J. Wade, R.G. Henzell, D.R. Younger, J. Warren, and
550 A.B. Dale. 1989. Genotype by environment interaction in grain sorghum II: effects of
551 temperature and photoperiod on ontogeny. *Crop Sci.* 29:376-384.
- 552 Holzworth, D.P., and G.L. Hammer. 1996. DEVEL2-a crop development-modelling tool: users guide,
553 Agricultural production systems research unit, Toowoomba, Australia.
- 554 Jones, C.A., and J.R. Kiniry. 1986. CERES-Maize: a simulation model of maize growth and
555 development. Texas A&M University Press, College Station, U.S.A.
- 556 Kassam, A.H., and D.J. Andrews. 1975. Effects of sowing date on growth, development and yield of
557 photosensitive sorghum at Samaru, northern Nigeria. *Expl. Agric.* 11:227-240.
- 558 Klein, R. R., J.E. Mullet, D.R. Jordan, F.R. Miller, W.L. Rooney, M.A. Menz, C.D. Franks, and P.E.
559 Klein. 2008. The effect of tropical sorghum conversion and inbred development on genome
560 diversity as revealed by high-resolution genotyping. *Crop Sci* 48(Supplement_1):S12-S26.
- 561 Kouressy, M., M. Dingkuhn, M. Vaksman, and A.B. Heinemann. 2008. Adaptation to diverse semi-
562 arid environments of sorghum genotypes having different plant type and sensitivity to
563 photoperiod. *Agric. Forest Meteor.* 148:357-371.
- 564 Lobell, D., G.L. Hammer, K. Chenu, B. Zheng, G. McLean, and S.C. Chapman. 2015. The shifting
565 influence of drought and heat stress for crops in northeast Australia. *Global Change Biol.*
566 21:4115–4127.

- 567 Mace, E.S., L. Xia, D.R. Jordan, D. R., K. Halloran, D.K. Parh, E. Huttner, P. Wenzl, and A. Kilian.
568 2008. DArT markers: diversity analyses and mapping in sorghum bicolor. BMC Genomics
569 9:26.
- 570 Major, D.J. 1980. Photoperiod response characteristics controlling flowering of nine crop spices. Can.
571 J. Plant Sci. 60:777-784.
- 572 Miller, F.R., D.K. Barnes, and H.J. Cruzado. 1968. Effect of tropical photoperiods on the growth of
573 sorghum when grown in 12 monthly plantings. Crop Sci. 8:499-502.
- 574 Muchow, R.C., and P.S. Carberry. 1990. Phenology and leaf area development in a tropical grain
575 sorghum. Field Crops Res. 23:221-237.
- 576 Nida, H., A. Tirfessa, A. Gebreyohannes, A. Nega, A. Seyoum, and T. Bejiga. 2014. Ethiopian
577 sorghum and millets improvement projects, Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research,
578 Addis Ababa, Ethiopia
- 579 Parent, B., and F. Tardieu. 2012. Temperature responses of developmental process have not been
580 affected by breeding in different ecological areas for 17 crop species. New Phyt. 194:760-
581 774.
- 582 Paterson, A.H., J.E. Bowers, R. Bruggmann, I. Dubchak, J. Grimwood, H. Gundlach, G. Haberer, U.
583 Hellsten, T. Mitros, A. Poliakov, J. Schmutz, M. Spannagl, H. Tang, X. Wang, T. Wicker,
584 A.K. Bharti, J. Chapman, F.A. Feltus, U. Gowik, I.V. Grigoriev, E. Lyons, C.A. Maher, M.
585 Martis, A. Narechania, R.P. Otilar, B.W. Penning, A.A. Salamov, Y. Wang, L. Zhang, N.C.
586 Carpita, M. Freeling, A.R. Gingle, C.T. Hash, B. Keller, P. Klein, S. Kresovich, M.C.
587 McCann, R. Ming, D.G. Peterson, M. ur-Rahman, D. Ware, P. Westhoff, K.F.X. Mayer, J.
588 Messing, and D.S. Rokhsar. 2009. The *Sorghum bicolor* genome and the diversification of
589 grasses. Nature 457:551-556.
- 590 Perrier, X., and J.P. Jacquemoud-Collet. 2006. DARwin Software. <http://darwin.cirad.fr/darwin>.

- 591 Quinby, J.R., J.D. Hesketh, and R.L. Voigt. 1973. Influence of temperature and photoperiod on floral
592 initiation and leaf number in sorghum. *Crop Sci.* 13:243-246.
- 593 Rattunde, H.F.W., E. Weltzien, B. Diallo, A.G. Diallo, M. Sidibe, A.O. Touré, A. Rathore, R.R. Das,
594 W.L. Leiser, and A. Touré. 2013. Yield of photoperiod-sensitive sorghum hybrids based on
595 Guinea-race germplasm under farmers' field conditions in Mali. *Crop Sci.* 53:2454-2461.
- 596 Ravi Kumar, S., G.L. Hammer, I. Broad, P. Harland, and G. McLean. 2009. Modelling environmental
597 effects on phenology and canopy development of diverse sorghum genotypes. *Field Crops*
598 *Res.* 111:157-165.
- 599 Roberts, E.H., A. Qi, R.H. Ellis, R.J. Summerfield, R.J. Lawn, and S. Shanmugasundaram. 1996. Use
600 of field observations to characterise genotypic flowering responses to photoperiod and
601 temperature: a soyabean exemplar. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 93:519-533.
- 602 SAS Institute Inc. (2013). SAS Version 9.4, Cary, NC: SAS Institute Inc.
- 603 Singh, S.P. 1985. Sources of cold tolerance in grain sorghum. *Can. J. Plant Sci.* 65, 251-257.
- 604 Singh, V., C.T. Nguyen, G. McLean, S.C. Chapman, B. Zheng, E.J. van Oosterom, and G.L. Hammer.
605 2017. Quantifying high temperature risks and their potential effects on sorghum production
606 in Australia. *Field Crops Res.* 211:77-88.
- 607 Sokal, R.R., and C.D. Michener. 1958. A statistical method for evaluating systematic relationships.
608 *The University of Kansas Science Bulletin*, 22:1409-1438.
- 609 Tessio, T., I. Kapran, C. Grenier, A. Snow, P. Sweeney, J. Pederson, D. Marx, G. Bothma, and G.
610 Ejeta. 2008. The potential for crop-to-wild gene flow in sorghum in Ethiopia and Niger: a
611 geographic survey. *Crop Sci.* 48:1425-1431.
- 612 van Oosterom, E.J., A.K. Borrell, S.C. Chapman, I.J. Broad, and G.L. Hammer. 2010. Functional
613 dynamics of the nitrogen balance of sorghum. I. N demand of vegetative plant parts. *Field*
614 *Crops Res.* 115:19-28.

615 Wade, L.J., G.L. Hammer, and M.A. Davey. 1993. Response of germination to temperature amongst
616 diverse sorghum hybrids. *Field Crops Res.* 31:295-308.

617 Yang, Z., E.J. van Oosterom, D.R. Jordan, A. Doherty, and G.L. Hammer. 2010. Genetic variation in
618 potential kernel size affects kernel growth and yield of sorghum. *Crop Sci.* 50:685-695.

619

620 **Figure 1.** (A) Average monthly maximum and minimum temperatures at Melkassa (solid line) and
 621 Kulumsa (dotted line) for the two years of experimentation. (B) Average monthly photoperiod
 622 (including twilight) at the two locations. The dashed line at the top of panel B indicates the range in
 623 sowing dates of 24 March to 25 July across the two years.

624

625 **Figure 2.** Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) for 553 sorghum genotypes based on 5,382 SNPs.
 626 Genotypes are colour-coded according to racial classification as indicated. The 18 triangles represent
 627 genotypes that were included in the experiments, whereas circles represent genotypes that were not
 628 included in the experiments, but included in the overall genetic diversity analysis for global context.

629

630 **Figure 3.** Average rate of development from emergence to anthesis versus average photoperiod and
 631 average temperature over that period for Meko and Jigurti for experiments conducted at Melkassa (○)
 632 and Kulumsa (●).

633

634 **Figure 4.** Sum of squares of residuals (SSR) versus common optimum temperature (T_{opt}) value
 635 associated with fit of the phenology model across all genotypes.

636

637 **Figure 5.** Predicted versus observed days to anthesis for 19 genotypes. Colour coded dots represent
 638 the 19 genotypes. Solid line represents the 1:1 relationship.

639

640 **Figure 6.** Thermal time from flag leaf to anthesis plotted against T_{base} for 19 genotypes representing
 641 adaptation to four agroecologies: dry lowland (○), wet lowlands (■), intermediate altitude (□), and
 642 highlands (●).

643

644 Table 1. Percentage of genome membership of racial group defined through STRUCTURE analysis for genotypes in the phenology study. Percentage of
645 genome membership below 5% is not included.

Genotype	Agroecology	Germplasm type	East African durra	Ethiopian highland durra	Caudatum	Kafir	Guinea
<i>Caudatum</i>							
Gambella1107	Dry lowlands	Released	-	-	99.9%	-	-
Macia	Dry lowlands	Released	-	-	96.9%	-	-
Meko	Dry lowlands	Released	-	-	99.9%	-	-
Melkam	Dry lowlands	Released	-	-	99.9%	-	-
Teshale	Dry lowlands	Released	-	-	99.0%	-	-
<i>Ethiopian highland durra</i>							
Alemaya70	Highland	Improved landrace	-	99.9%	-	-	-
Chelenko	Highland	Improved landrace	-	99.1%	-	-	-

Chiro	Highland	Improved landrace	-	99.7%	-	-	-
ETS 2752	Highland	Improved landrace	-	99.9%	-	-	-
Degalit	Dry lowlands	Landrace	-	99.9%	-	-	-
Jamiyu	Dry lowlands	Landrace	-	91.2%	-	-	-
Jigurti	Dry lowlands	Landrace	-	99.9%	-	-	-
<i>Kafir</i>							
Birmash	Intermediate	Released	-	-	-	94.1%	-
Dagem	Intermediate	Released	-	-	-	99.9%	-
Geremew	Intermediate	Released	-	11.0%	7.1%	80.7%	-
IS9302	Intermediate	Released	-	-	-	99.9%	-
<i>caudatum/guinea</i>							
Adukara	Wet lowlands	Landrace	13.1%	10.5%	49.6%	-	22.2%
Bobere	Wet lowlands	Landrace	7.2%	7.6%	63.1%	-	21.5%

Unknown

ESH-2	Dry lowlands	Released	-	-	-	-	-
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647 Table 2. Rate of development (R_{opt}), base temperature (T_{base}), goodness of fit (R^2) from emergence to
 648 anthesis and thermal time (TT) from flag leaf to anthesis fitted for key Ethiopian genotypes, grown
 649 for two years across two locations in Ethiopia with six sowing dates per year and location. The bottom
 650 part of the table provides values for each racial group, averaged across the genotypes for that group.

Genotype	Agroecology	n	R_{opt} (day^{-1}) ^a	T_{base} ($^{\circ}C$) ^a	R^2	TT ($^{\circ}Cd$) ^a
<i>caudatum</i>						
Gambella1107	Dry lowlands	23	0.017	0.9	0.87	271
Macia	Dry lowlands	23	0.019	4.1	0.92	246
Meko	Dry lowlands	23	0.022	6.0	0.91	201
Melkam	Dry lowlands	23	0.018	0.0	0.89	304
Teshale	Dry lowlands	23	0.019	1.3	0.87	280
<i>Ethiopian highland durra</i>						
Alemaya 70	Highland	23	0.013	3.4	0.82	256
Chelenko	Highland	22	0.011	0.1	0.90	322
Chiro	Highland	23	0.012	1.5	0.79	315
ETS2752	Highland	23	0.012	0.0	0.81	311
Degalit	Dry lowlands	22	0.015	5.5	0.86	217
Jamiyu	Dry lowlands	23	0.016	5.4	0.91	233
Jigurti	Dry lowlands	23	0.018	6.6	0.89	189
<i>kafir</i>						

Birmash	Intermediate	23	0.019	9.8	0.97	152
Dagem	Intermediate	23	0.017	9.0	0.91	151
Geremew	Intermediate	23	0.015	7.2	0.93	199
IS9302	Intermediate	23	0.018	9.4	0.93	156
<i>caudatum/guinea</i>						
Adukara	Wet lowlands	16	0.011	8.9	0.89	153
Bobo red	Wet lowlands	20	0.013	7.3	0.82	187
<i>unknown</i>						
ESH 2	Dry lowlands	23	0.020	0.4	0.89	303
<i>Averages</i>						
<i>caudatum</i>	Dry lowlands	5	0.019a	2.46cd		260ab
<i>durra</i>	Highland	4	0.012b	1.25d		301a
<i>durra</i>	Dry lowlands	3	0.016a	5.83bc		213bc
<i>kafir</i>	Intermediate	4	0.017a	8.85a		165d
<i>caudatum/guinea</i>	Wet lowlands	2	0.012b	8.10ab		170cd

651 ^a Racial group means followed by a different letter differ significantly (P<0.05) based on t-test using
652 the pooled method for equal variances.

653

654

655 Table 3. Rate of development (R_{opt}) and goodness of fit (R^2) from anthesis to maturity for key
 656 Ethiopian sorghum germplasm, grown for two years across two locations in Ethiopia with six sowing
 657 dates per year and location.

Genotype	Agroecology	n	R_{opt} (day ⁻¹)	R^2
<i>caudaum</i>				
Gambella 1107	Dry lowlands	23	0.024	0.81
Macia	Dry lowlands	23	0.023	0.63
Meko	Dry lowlands	22	0.021	0.55
Melkam	Dry lowlands	23	0.022	0.67
Teshale	Dry lowlands	23	0.022	0.70
<i>Ethiopian highland durra</i>				
Alemaya 70	Highland	21	0.021	0.29
Chelenko	Highland	19	0.024	0.42
Chiro	Highland	-	-	-
ETS 2752	Highland	22	0.022	0.39
Degalit	Dry lowlands	21	0.021	0.26
Jamiyu	Dry lowlands	22	0.022	0.71
Jigurti	Dry lowlands	22	0.021	0.45
<i>kafir</i>				
Birmash	Intermediate	21	0.022	0.11
Dagem	Intermediate	22	0.022	0.25

Geremew	Intermediate	20	0.022	0.19
IS 9302	Intermediate	22	0.021	0.31
<i>caudatum/guinea</i>				
Adukara	Wet lowlands	-	-	-
Bobe red	Wet lowlands	-	-	-
<i>unknown</i>				
ESH 2	Dry lowlands	22	0.021	0.63

658

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

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2 Figure 6

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